

Artificial Intelligence & Its Applications

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Abstract:

It is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs. It is related to the similar task of using computers to understand human intelligence, but AI does not have to confine itself to methods that are biologically observable. While no consensual definition of Artificial Intelligence (AI) exists, AI is broadly characterized as the study of computations that allow for perception, reason and action. Today, the amount of data that is generated, by both humans and machines, far outpaces humans' ability to absorb, interpret, and make complex decisions based on that data. Artificial intelligence forms the basis for all computer learning and is the future of all complex decision making. This paper examines features of artificial Intelligence, introduction, definitions of AI, history, applications, growth and achievements.

Keywords: *Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Neural Networks, Natural Language Processing and Knowledge Base System*

Introduction:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the branch of computer science which deals with intelligence of machines where an intelligent agent is a system that takes actions which maximize its chances of success. It is the study of ideas which enable computers to do the things that make people seem intelligent. The central principles of AI include such as reasoning, knowledge, planning, learning, communication, perception and the ability to move and manipulate objects. It is the science and engineering of making intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs.

Artificial Intelligence Methods:

Machine Learning: It is one of the applications of AI where machines are not explicitly programmed to perform certain tasks; rather, they learn and improve from experience automatically. Deep Learning is a subset of machine learning

based on artificial neural networks for predictive analysis.

Automation & Robotics: The purpose of Automation is to get the monotonous and repetitive tasks done by machines which also improve productivity and in receiving cost-effective and more efficient results.

Machine Vision:

Machines can capture visual information and then analyze it. Here cameras are used to capture the visual information, the analogue to digital conversion is used to convert the image to digital data, and digital signal processing is employed to process the data. Then the resulting data is fed to a computer. In machine vision, two vital aspects are sensitivity, which is the ability of the machine to perceive impulses that are weak and resolution, the range to which the machine can distinguish the objects. The usage of machine vision can be found in signature identification,

pattern recognition, and medical image analysis, etc.

Knowledge-Based Systems (KBS):

A KBS can be defined as a computer system capable of giving advice in a particular domain, utilizing knowledge provided by a human expert. A distinguishing feature of KBS lies in the separation behind the knowledge, which can be represented in a number of ways such as rules, frames, or cases, and the inference engine or algorithm which uses the knowledge base to arrive at a conclusion.

Neural Networks:

NNs are biologically inspired systems consisting of a massively connected network of computational “neurons,” organized in layers. By adjusting the weights of the network, NNs can be “trained” to approximate virtually any nonlinear function to a required degree of accuracy. NNs typically are provided with a set of input and output exemplars. A learning algorithm (such as back propagation) would then be used to adjust the weights in the network so that the network would give the desired output, in a type of learning commonly called supervised learning.

Applications of AI:

Following are some sectors which have the application of Artificial Intelligence:

Artificial Intelligence has various applications in today's society. It is becoming essential for today's time because it can solve complex problems with an efficient way in multiple industries, such as Healthcare, entertainment, finance, education, etc. AI is making our daily life more comfortable and fast.

1. AI in Astronomy: Artificial Intelligence can be very useful to solve complex universe problems. AI technology can be helpful for

understanding the universe such as how it works, origin, etc.

- 2. AI in Healthcare:** In the last, five to ten years, AI becoming more advantageous for the healthcare industry and going to have a significant impact on this industry. Healthcare Industries are applying AI to make a better and faster diagnosis than humans. AI can help doctors with diagnoses and can inform when patients are worsening so that medical help can reach to the patient before hospitalization.
- 3. AI in Gaming:** AI can be used for gaming purpose. The AI machines can play strategic games like chess, where the machine needs to think of a large number of possible places.
- 4. AI in Finance:** AI and finance industries are the best matches for each other. The finance industry is implementing automation, chatbot, adaptive intelligence, algorithm trading, and machine learning into financial processes.
- 5. AI in Data Security:** The security of data is crucial for every company and cyber-attacks are growing very rapidly in the digital world. AI can be used to make your data more safe and secure. Some examples such as AEG bot, AI2 Platform, are used to determine software bug and cyber-attacks in a better way.
- 6. AI in Social Media:** Social Media sites such as Facebook, Twitter, and Snapchat contain billions of user profiles, which need to be stored and managed in a very efficient way. AI can organize and manage massive amounts of data. AI can analyze lots of data to identify the latest trends, hashtag, and requirement of different users. AI is becoming highly demanding for travel industries. AI is capable of doing various travel related works such as from making travel arrangement to suggesting the hotels, flights, and best routes to the customers.

7. AI in Travel & Transport

8. AI in Automotive Industry

9. **AI in Robotics:** Artificial Intelligence has a remarkable role in Robotics. Usually, general robots are programmed such that they can perform some repetitive task, but with the help of AI, we can create intelligent robots which can perform tasks with their own experiences without pre-programmed. Humanoid Robots are best examples for AI in robotics, recently the intelligent Humanoid robot named as Erica and Sophia has been developed which can talk and behave like humans.

10. AI in Entertainment

11. **AI in Agriculture:** Agriculture is an area which requires various resources, labor, money, and time for best result. Now a day's agriculture is becoming digital, and AI is emerging in this field. Agriculture is applying AI as agriculture robotics, solid and crop monitoring, predictive analysis. AI in agriculture can be very helpful for farmers.

12. **AI in E-commerce:** AI is providing a competitive edge to the e-commerce industry, and it is becoming more demanding in the e-commerce business. AI is helping shoppers to discover associated products with recommended size, color, or even brand.

13. **AI in education:** AI can automate grading so that the tutor can have more time to teach. AI chatbot can communicate with students as a teaching assistant. o AI in the future can be work as a personal virtual tutor for students, which will be accessible easily at any time and any place.

Some Other Applications:

1. **Fraud detection:** The financial services industry uses artificial intelligence in two ways. Initial scoring of applications for credit uses AI to understand creditworthiness. More

advanced AI engines are employed to monitor and detect fraudulent payment card transactions in real time.

2. **Virtual customer assistance (VCA):** Call centers use VCA to predict and respond to customer inquiries outside of human interaction. Voice recognition, coupled with simulated human dialog, is the first point of interaction in a customer service inquiry. Higher-level inquiries are redirected to a human.

3. **Medicine:** A medical clinic can use AI systems to organize bed schedules, make a staff rotation, and provide medical information. AI has also application in fields of cardiology (CRG), neurology (MRI), embryology (sonography), complex operations of internal organs etc.

4. **Heavy Industries:** Huge machines involve risk in their manual maintenance and working. So in becomes necessary part to have an efficient and safe operation agent in their operation.

5. **Telecommunications:** Many telecommunications companies make use of heuristic search in the management of their work forces for example BT Group has deployed heuristic search in a scheduling application that provides the work schedules of 20000 engineers.

6. **Music:** Scientists are trying to make the computer emulate the activities of the skillful musician. Composition, performance, music theory, sound processing are some of the major areas on which research in Music and Artificial Intelligence are focusing on. Eg: chucks, Orchextra, smartmusic etc.

7. **Antivirus:** Artificial intelligence (AI) techniques have played increasingly important role in antivirus detection. At present, some principal artificial intelligence techniques applied in antivirus detection It

improves the performance of antivirus detection systems, and promotes the production of new artificial intelligence algorithm and the application in antivirus detection to integrate antivirus detection with artificial intelligence.

Future of AI:

Looking at the features and its wide application we may definitely stick to artificial intelligence. Seeing at the development of AI, is it that the future world is becoming artificial. Biological intelligence is fixed, because it is an old, mature paradigm, but the new paradigm of non-biological computation and intelligence is growing exponentially. The memory capacity of the human brain is probably of the order of ten thousand million binary digits. But most of this is probably used in remembering visual impressions, and other comparatively wasteful ways. Hence we can say that as natural intelligence is limited and volatile too world may now depend upon computers for smooth working. Artificial intelligence (AI) is truly a revolutionary feat of computer science, set to become a core component of all modern software over the coming years and decades.

Conclusion:

Till now we have discussed in brief about Artificial Intelligence. We have discussed some of its principles, its applications, its achievements etc. The ultimate goal of institutions and scientists working on AI is to solve majority of the problems or to achieve the tasks which we humans directly can't accomplish. It is for sure that development in this field of computer science will change the complete scenario of the world Now it is the responsibility of creamy layer of engineers to develop this field.

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